

THE ONLINE FORUM AND OTHER E-TOOLS WHICH THEY INCLUDED IN WRITING COMMUNICATIVE FRAMEWORK

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Abstract: There have been numerous approaches to the teaching of writing in the history of language teaching. These writing approaches have evolved with the development of different approaches to teaching in general, which have in turn contributed to the changing role and status of writing.

Key words: The pedagogical approaches, Product, Process, Post-Process, Socio-cultural and genre approaches, process-oriented writing.

There have been numerous approaches to the teaching of writing in the history of language teaching. These writing approaches have evolved with the development of different approaches to teaching in general, which have in turn contributed to the changing role and status of writing [10;25]. The pedagogical approaches to second language writing emerged at different times since 1960's. They are Product, Process, Post-Process, Socio-cultural and genre approaches which have contributed to the development of the writing pedagogy. The rise of the process approach marks the beginning of a new era for second language writing pedagogy. The traditional product-oriented view of writing which regards writing as linear and fragmented procedure is thus contrary to the actual writing process. In process-oriented writing, writers are able to make modifications to the written text or make changes in their original plans as they review their writing.

Modern society places high demands on education and overall development of students. So it requires an effectiveness of the assimilation program. Every child must be taught in a short period of time to obtain process, evaluate and use in practice a large amount of information. It is important to organize the learning process so that the child has to actively work with interest and enthusiasm in the classroom, saw the fruits of their labor and could independently assess them. [33; 18]

To help the teacher in addressing this challenge may blend the traditional teaching methods and modern information technologies, including computer and using Internet resources. Using a computer in the classroom enables the process of learning mobile strictly differentiated, individual and interactive.

Modern computer combines the capabilities of your TV, VCR, books, calculator, phone, and is a versatile tool that can simulate different language situations, it can quickly and efficiently respond to inquiries and actions of the student. This method of learning is also very attractive to teachers:

helps them to better assess the ability and knowledge of the child. It encourages the search for new, non-traditional forms and methods of teaching, gives scope for pedagogical creativity. So the computer does not replace teachers, but complements it by playing the role of a tool that when used properly it greatly improves the efficiency of the pedagogical process.

With the advent of computer networks widely available in educational institutions and at home students and teachers have gained the opportunity to quickly obtain the necessary

information from any point on the globe. Through its global telecommunications network is possible with instant access to global information resources.

There are several thousand files in English published Online, containing the training-methodical and scientific information that allows you to organize operational advice, model research activities, conduct virtual training sessions (workshops, lectures) in real time. With through these sites, you can find a large number of materials to improve the writing skills that will be a rich resource for learning.

Teachers are able to use materials of various domestic and foreign websites in preparation for the English lesson. British Council carried out an internet survey of teachers to find out: what Internet resources are often used in training. Among the most commonly used teacher called chats, online dictionaries, blogs and virtual learning environments. 10% of respondents do not use the Internet in the classroom.

If English teachers having trouble in using the Internet resources in the classroom and in preparation for it, the site Media Awareness Network (<http://www.media-awareness.ca/english/teachers>), you can find detailed lessons with a phased development, identifying actions as well as materials for self-education and improvement of professional skills of the teacher. The site contains articles by foreign trainers, practitioners working with Internet technologies and developing their own courses. In addition, site developers and consultants are ready to answer the any questions. The site has a special section for parents, which examines issues such as the safety of children using the Internet, privacy, and ethics of communication in virtual communities. The website teaches to analyze and evaluate the information that we face when working on the Internet. An access to the site is free.

With the support of the British Council created a series of sites for teachers and for those who are learning English. The website - Teaching English (<http://www.teachingenglish.org.uk>) was specifically designed for teachers of English. There are articles of Methodists devoted to teaching various aspects of the language. Community forum of students with teachers and supervisors from around the world gives an opportunity to discuss any issues.

The site “write-site.athabasca.ca” is designed to assist students with academic writing assignments. Students can use this service to receive feedback about the writing component – organization, mechanics, grammar, and style – of an assignment before they submit it to a tutor for marking. Write site is designed to help students develop their writing skills within the context of course work over time. Coaches will help students identify individual patterns of errors in their writing, and work with them on no more than three or four skills with each submission.

There is also a good one “Writerscafe.org” which I describe it as an online community for writers. If you wonder what other people would think of your writing or if you are looking for some constructive criticism this site is suitable one. At writerscafe.org they offer several tools for you to improve your writing. Readers can rate, review, and add notes to your writing. You can track how readers rate your writing with their snazzy graphs. And the “share” buttons allow you to send your writing to all your friends (both on WritersCafe.org and off). The most important part of WritersCafe.org what it is: a friendly community where people – friends - can offer advice, share ideas, and encourage you in your writing.

In WritersCafe.org you can create your particular group to use for your own purpose. As for teachers it would be one of the best tools to operate with lessons. Carrying out my research

I have found it as an effective way or approach using this kind of group where you can teach your students within the classroom environment create a comfort, economize your time and use it for your benefit. While creating the group you can select an audience as (everyone, teen, adult) after putting your name. There are special genres or types of writing which you will use, especially write and discuss in your group. You can choose who can post their comments who cannot.

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